

Second Sheld-on conference meeting
Solutions for ageing well at home, in the community and at work
Proceedings Book

Ohrid 17th October 2019

COST Action CA16226

Indoor living space improvement: Smart Habitat for the Elderly

Sheld-on

Furniture, Habitat, Active and Healthy Ageing, ICT, Healthcare

Proceedings of the COST Action CA16226 conference meeting,
Ohrid, North Macedonia, 17th October 2019.

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Preface

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the Second Sheld-on Conference Meeting promoted by the COST Action CA16226: "Indoor living space improvement: Smart habitat for the elderly". This time it will be held in Ohrid, North Macedonia, on the 17th of October, 2019, collocated with the 11th ICT Innovations Conference 2019.

This conference follows almost two years of active collaboration under three different working groups focused in vertical areas of knowledge. This paved the way for a new horizontal working group that aims for deeper interdisciplinary interactions and knowledge interchange considering the broad concept of "Solutions for Ageing Well". Due to its broad spectrum, its structure contains three subworking groups looking into narrower areas of application, specifically at home, work and the community. A fourth one focuses on the important topic of "Technology Adoption". The proceedings and conference parallel tracks reflect this new approach.

This conference brings together researchers not only from Sheld-on members, but also from other institutions that work in related fields, some of which bring results achieved during the Short Term Scientific Mission granted by Sheld-on during the last year. A total of 31 papers cover a wide range of topics within the scope of Sheld-on, including IoT, BIM, connected health, features of the elderly and their relation to technology, applications of robots, and many others such as social aspects, climate change and artificial intelligence. Each work has been peer-reviewed by two carefully selected experts.

This event will be a great opportunity not only to plan for the action work in the near future, but also to advance the Sheld-on collaborative effort to build new solutions that contribute to the well-being of older adults and their caretakers, while addressing the socioeconomics concerns related to a worldwide aging population.

We would like to thank the local organization staff from the Association for Information and Communication Technologies and the Sts. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia, the members of the scientific committee for their review work and suggestions for improving the papers, the authors for contributing their research results to the conference, and all Sheld-on members for supporting and publicising the event.

Special thanks to the COST association that has made possible all activities of the Sheld-on Action, including this conference, and has initiated other derived initiatives and fruitful collaborations.

On behalf of the core group,
Rafael Maestre, Working Group 4 Leader
Francisco Melero, Action Chair

Index

Solutions for ageing well at home

- 1/8 Telepresence mobile robot platform for elderly care | **6** |
- 2/8 BIM & AAL | **9** |
- 3/8 Interactive textiles for designing adaptive space for elderly | **13** |
- 4/8 Solutions in built environment to prevent social isolation | **15** |
- 5/8 Smart furniture definition based on key technologies specification in context of literature and patent analysis | **19** |
- 6/8 A short history of IoT architectures through real AAL Cases | **24** |
- 7/8 Resource Allocation using network Centrality in the AAL environment | **28** |
- 8/8 Framework for the development of mobile AAL applications | **32** |

Solutions for ageing well in the community

- 1/10 The use of Technology to promote activity and communication by the municipality services, examples from an urban area | **36** |
- 2/10 Thermal environment assessment and adaptative model analysis in elderly centers in the Atlantic climate | **42** |
- 3/10 Climate change in the city and the elderlies | **46** |
- 4/10 Loneliness is not simply being alone. How understand the loneliness in ageing to create smart environments | **50** |
- 5/10 From Co-design to Industry: investigating both ends of the scale of developing Social Robots | **53** |
- 6/10 Thermal comfort perception in elderly care centers. Case study of Lithuania | **57** |
- 7/10 Human – machine interaction - Assessment of seniors' characteristics and its importance for predicting performance patterns | **60** |
- 8/10 Potential biomarkers and risk factors associated with frailty syndrome in older adults – preliminary results from the BioFrail study | **63** |

- 9/10 Consciousness Society creation. Stage development | **65** |
- 10/10 Attempts to improve the situation of elderly people in the Republic of Moldova | **68** |

Solutions for ageing well at work

- 1/6 Quantitative analysis of publications on policies for ageing at work | **72** |
- 2/6 Can deep learning contribute to healthy aging at work? | **75** |
- 3/6 Work and social activity for longer healthy life | **78** |
- 4/6 Reverse mentoring as an alternative strategy for lifelong learning in the workplace | **81** |
- 5/6 What users want – research on workers, employers and caregivers demands on SmartWork AI system | **84** |
- 6/6 Healthy aging at work: Trends in scientific publications | **88** |

Technology Adoption

- 1/7 Challenges in Building AI-Based Connected Health Services for Older Adults | **93** |
- 2/7 Connected Health and Wellbeing for People with Complex Communication Needs | **96** |
- 3/7 Analysis on competences and needs of senior citizens related to domotics | **99** |
- 4/7 Comparison of technology adoption models | **103** |
- 5/7 Choice architecture to promote the adoption of new technologies | **107** |
- 6/7 Swallowing the bitter pill: Emotional barriers to the adoption of medicine compliance systems among older adults | **110** |
- 7/7 An Edge Computing Robot Experience for Automatic Elderly Mental Health Care Based on Voice | **114** |

Technology Adoption

Sub-Working Group 4.4 Proceedings

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Second Sheld-on conference meeting
Proceedings Book

Choice architecture to promote the adoption of new technologies

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It is difficult to predict to what extent and how fast new technologies will be adopted. Amongst older adults, we know technology adoption lags behind many other demographics (Lee and Coughlin 2015). This poses significant barriers in delivering solutions to a user group that can benefit significantly from recent advances in robotics, artificial intelligence, Internet of Things, and other digital assisted living technologies.

Technology adoption is limited due to many factors, including privacy and security concerns, as many of the solutions monitor users (i.e., for fall detection or to predict health events) and therefore mean collecting and sharing personal data (Chaudhuri et al. 2014). Issues around stigma, access to support, and anxiety about using devices are barriers as well (Chaudhuri et al. 2014). Solutions for older adults may be further limited because product designers (typically younger, technologically capable adults) may not be closely familiar with the characteristics and needs of the intended users (older adults) (Lee and Coughlin 2015). Recent strides in requirements engineering may help bridge the gap between the needs perceived by designers and the actual physical and emotional needs of the users (Taveter et al. 2012; Lopez-lorca et al. 2014). If user needs are addressed well by a solution, what can be done to improve its uptake?

One of the major obstacles stalling technology acceptance across all demographics stems from human cognitive biases. Particularly responsible is the status quo bias, where the current state of affairs is preferred and any change from that state is perceived as a loss (Samuelson and Zeckhauser 1988). Users may therefore resist adopting the new technology even if it can address their needs (Kim and Kankanhalli 2009). In healthcare facilities, for example, potential users sometimes resist adopting technologies that could considerably improve organizational functioning (Bhattacharjee and Hikmet 2007). Widespread implementation of assistive technologies for older adults may face similar adoption resistance. For instance, it has been observed that resistance to change in older adults is associated with lower willingness to adopt preventative mobile health services (Hoque and Sorwar 2017). Promoting the use of technology can thus provide only limited gains if it is based only on technological aspects and does not consider user resistance fuelled by the status quo bias.

A recent study has demonstrated how a slight manipulation in the choice architecture – the way choices are presented – can alleviate such user resistance and nudge people to more frequently favour the new technology (Stryja et al. 2017). Thoughtful design of choice architecture thus has the potential to decrease the older adults' resistance to adopting helpful assistive technologies. The presentation of choices could be improved with greater understanding of the general human nature and the specific characteristics of the target users. The insights elicited during the requirements engineering phase could not only be useful in designing products but also in designing choices that the intended users will face.

Our analysis of choice architecture design will include the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT). Carefully structured choices can provide guidance in decision-ma-

king process, but it may not be easy to design them. And while devising choices offers many opportunities for positive change, it is important to be mindful of the potential risks when the choice architecture does not act in the best interest of users.

In the world of behavioural economics, it has long been recognized that humans are rarely rational agents, whose decision-making hinges on careful analysis of the available evidence. Human biases have long been exploited in modern advertising that often encourages activities that are harmful to health. Similar approaches could be applied to promote health benefiting activities and tools, including the use of assistive technology, which must be adopted more widely to achieve the greatest impact. One valuable tool may be carefully designed choice architecture that accompanies a technological solution in the promotion phase.

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